

LINGUISTICS

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Annotation: *linguistics or linguistics studies and analyzes the weapon of communication, which is a kind of complex social phenomenon - language as a system - as a whole object. In the Aupi process, it is observed in various manifestations, forms. It follows from the essence of the eda language to the social character, from the fact that it must be turned, checked from different sides, and this is absolutely correct from the point of view of the point of view of science.*

Keywords: *Linguistics, languages, learning, fields.*

Linguistics is a science that studies languages. There are practical and theoretical types of linguistics, theoretical linguistics studies the structure (grammar) of a language and its meaning (semantics). Grammar-covers the disciplines of morphology (structure and change of words), syntax (rules for combining words into phrases and sentences) and Phonology (learning a language using abstract sounds). Applied linguistics is mainly concerned with the application of theoretical knowledge learned in linguistics in practice. Applied Linguistics includes the study and teaching of foreign languages.

"Linguistics" is the science of language, its social nature, function, internal structure, classification, laws of action (activity) of certain languages, historical progress. According to the purpose and task, there are several areas (areas) of linguistics: general linguistics is a field that studies language as a human - specific phenomenon in general, the main task of which is to identify and illuminate the most common character-features characteristic of world languages; private linguistics is a field that studies the character-characteristics of some language; applied linguistics direction of development of methods of processing; mathematical linguistics, structural linguistics, comparative-historical such areas as linguistics and other paralinguistics, ethnolinguistics, Psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics study the linguistic features associated with the activities of the speaker (person) in society.

In addition to these areas, linguistics has many branches and sections that study certain levels and units in each language: semasiology studies the meanings of language units; phonetics and Phonology examine the sound construction of a

language; lexicology and phraseology study the vocabulary material of a language. The object of study of Word formation is the methods of Word formation and the productivity of these methods, while grammar (morphology and syntax) studies word changes and the laws of the combination of words as sentences and word combinations. Each section of linguistics may have even smaller (smaller) special sections.

Dynamic linguistics, asosap, actively studies language in its Real existence, various tasks in the communicative process, "in progress", in change.

Static linguistics fully synchronized miauuap in language activity divides a period (fragment) and describes it. This area of linguistics, different from dynamic linguistics, completely deviates from the process of development and change in language, without convergence in the thread, examines the state of a certain "qag" part of the language in relation to the current - modern period

Sipxgop linguistics is inextricably linked with static and structural linguistics, serving to describe the "downy", "stagnant" state of the language at a certain period.

Diachron linguistics is inextricably linked with dynamic and atomistic linguistics, studying the development of language, and the laws and results of the development of language units.

Internal linguistics studies the system connection, relationship of linguistic units without dependence on extralinguistic factors. The research source of internal linguistics is phonology, lexicology and grammar.

USED LITERATURE:

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